

THE ANALYSIS OF BONDED LAP JOINTS

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SUMMARY: Structural adhesives are being increasingly used in the joining of both primary and secondary aircraft structures. However, the properties of film adhesives (eg. FM 73) have been shown to demonstrate significant time dependencies, even at room temperature. This paper investigates the impact of these time dependent properties on the structural behaviour of adhesively bonded joints. To this end a series of finite element analysis were conducted where the time dependent properties of the adhesive were modelled using a unified plasticity theory. This work shows that, when performing certification assessments which require statements on the integrity and the durability of adhesively bonded joints subjected to complex load spectra, it may be necessary to consider an analysis which accounts for both time and load history effects.

KEYWORDS: bonded joints, composite repairs, certification, stress analysis

INTRODUCTION

When designing bonded repairs, or adhesively bonded joints, the stress/strain response of the adhesive plays a central role in determining both the load carrying capacity and the fatigue performance of the repair or joint, see [1, 2]. In recent years Chiu et al. [3] have developed a variant of the thick-adherend short over-lap adherend test specimen for characterising the stress/shear behaviour of thin film adhesives. The results revealed that the properties of the film adhesive FM73 were strongly time-dependent, even at room temperature. Chiu et al. [3] also used a unified constitutive model to describe the time dependent behaviour of the adhesive.

This paper assesses the significance of this time-dependent behaviour, in a realistic symmetric double lap joint, via a detailed finite element analysis. This study reveals that the stress/strain behaviour of the adhesive in a double lap joint is dependent on both the loading rate and the load history. When, at room temperature, the joint is subjected to monotonic loading with a constant loading rate the energy density at the worst point in the joint is almost time independent. However, it will be shown that when the joint is loaded monotonically but in a complex manner then the load history dependent properties of the adhesive can become significant. This effect has implications for the fatigue assessment of bonded joints. It thus appears that, when performing a certification assessment which requires statements of the integrity and durability of adhesively bonded joints subjected to complex load spectra, it may be necessary to consider an analysis which accounts for both time and load history effects.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In the past few years there has been an increasing interest in the use of unified constitutive models for predicting the non-linear response of structural materials. These models overcome many of the deficiencies of the classical approach to the inelastic behaviour of materials. They were originally developed to model the response of metals in the high temperature regime where creep and stress relaxation are particularly important [4]. Classical techniques of modelling plasticity have a high degree of accuracy provided the loading is monotonic. However, they become increasingly inaccurate when the material is subjected to cyclic loading. In order to overcome this shortcoming an extension of the unified constitutive model, originally developed by Ramaswamy [5], was used in this investigation. This model was an extension of the generic back stress (Ω_{ij}) and drag stress (Z) model proposed by Stouffer and Bodner [6]. The model was later shown to be applicable to a range of materials and has been extensively used within Australia, see Kuruppu, et al. [7] and Jones, et al. [2, 8, 9]. The Ramaswamy-Stouffer model has also been extended to describe the mechanical behaviour of thin film adhesives, see Chiu et al [3].

This formulation uses two internal state variables, back stress Ω_{ij} (deviatoric) tensor and drag stress Z to define the state of the material. Here the inelastic deformation is driven by the over stress which is defined as $(S_{ij} - \Omega_{ij})$. Similar types of theories have been widely used to describe the time dependent behaviour of thermoplastics. In this approach, the flow equation is defined as:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^i = D \exp \left[\frac{-A}{2} \left(\frac{Z^2}{3K_2} \right)^n \right] \frac{(S_{ij} - \Omega_{ij})}{\sqrt{K_2}} \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^i$ is the inelastic strain rate tensor, S_{ij} is the deviatoric stress and $K_2 = \frac{1}{2} (S_{ij} - \Omega_{ij})(S_{ij} - \Omega_{ij})$. Here D , A and n are material constants. The term $(S_{ij} - \Omega_{ij}) / \sqrt{K_2}$ in equation (1) is the normalised overstress and defines the straining direction. The drag stress is history dependent and evolves with the effective inelastic strain ϵ^i . The initial drag stress is Z_0 , final Z_1 , and m_0 controls the rate of evolution. The ‘‘growth’’ of the drag stress is defined by equation (2).

$$Z = Z_1 + (Z_0 - Z_1) e^{-m_0 \epsilon^i} \quad (2)$$

The back stress is initially zero and its evolution is controlled by an evolution equation, viz:

$$\dot{\Omega}_{ij} = f_2 \dot{S}_{ij} + f_1 \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^i - \frac{3}{2} f_1 \frac{\Omega_{ij}}{\Omega_{\max}} \dot{\epsilon}^i \quad (3)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}^i = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^i \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^i}$ is the effective inelastic strain rate. Here, f_1 , f_2 and Ω_{\max} are material constants. The effective inelastic strain rate is defined in the normal fashion.

VALIDATION OF MODEL

Consider the symmetric double lap joint shown in Figure 1. This joint has an overlap length of 90 mm, and consists of two identical aluminium adherends with an elastic modulus $E = 70000$ MPa, and $t=1.5$ mm. The aluminium adherends and doublers were assumed to be bonded together using a FM73 film adhesive. The adhesive, FM73 film, was 0.2 mm thick and had a shear modulus of 750 MPa and its behaviour may be described using the state variable formulation described above. Some typical material parameters for the constitutive law for FM73 at room temperature are given in Table 1. This joint was analysed using both the 1 dimensional formulation, referred to as BJ4C and described in detail in [8], and a variant of the modified ABAQUS analysis program described in [9]. In each case a remote stress of 401 MPa was assumed to be monotonically applied to the ends of the inner adherend with the load increasing from 0 to its maximum load in either 0.1 sec, 1 sec, 10 sec or 100 sec. A comparison of the calculated maximum mean shear strains γ in the joint is shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Some typical material parameters for FM73 film at room temperature, see [3]

	A	D	f_1 (MPa)	f_2	n	m_0	Ω_{max}	Z_0 (MPa)	Z_1 (MPa)
Room temp.	1	10000	800	0.2	0.85	10	12.5	120	350

Table 2: Comparison of mean shear strain γ with 1D Visco-Plastic Formulation, $L/2t = 15$

Dimension	Loading Time (sec)			
	0.1	1	10	100
1D algorithm	0.143	0.152	0.163	0.177
Finite element 2D/3D	0.152	0.165	0.179	0.189
% Diff	5.9	7.9	8.9	6.3

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of the symmetric double lap joint

ANALYSIS OF DOUBLE LAP JOINTS

Having thus validated the finite element implementation a further series of finite element analysis of various double lap joints (Figure 2) were then performed. The joints analysed in this paper had ($L/2t$) ratios of 7.5 and 15 and a range of load histories were evaluated. Due to symmetry, only a quarter of the double lap joint(s) needed to be modelled (Figure 2). These joints had overlap lengths of 90 mm (for $L/2t=15$), and 45 mm (for $L/2t=7.5$) respectively. The elastic modulus of the adherends was $E=70000$ MPa. The thicknesses were 3 mm (for the inner adherend) and 1.5 mm (for the doubler). The aluminium adherends and doublers were assumed to be bonded together using FM73. The FM73 adhesive was 0.2 mm thick and had a shear modulus of 750 MPa. These joints were loaded to a maximum remote stress of 401 MPa. with the load going from 0 load to its maximum value in either 0.1 sec, 1 sec, 10 sec or 100 sec. The stress/strain relationship at the worst (critical) point in the adhesive layer during these load up sequences is shown in Figures 3 ($L/2t=15$) and 4 ($L/2t=7.5$). These figures show that the stress/strain behaviour of the adhesive is dependent on the loading rate (the higher the loading rate, the higher is the apparent yield stress). The maximum stress level (apparent yield stress) in the adhesive is higher when the joint is loaded more rapidly. These figures also show that the strain level in the adhesive is dependent on the loading history. Here the higher loading rate resulted in lower adhesive strain levels. These results reveal the difficulties in assessing the conservativeness of any rate independent bonded joint analysis, or in determining the integrity of such a joint based on either the maximum stress or the maximum strain failure theories.

In contrast to the stress or strain based approaches, Hart-Smith's [4] analysis of a double lap joint, revealed that the load carrying capacity of the bond can be estimated from the energy density at the worst point in the adhesive. This design methodology was based on the assumption that the adhesive behaviour can be approximated with a single stress/strain curve. This simplification was not used in our analysis. Here, the adhesive was allowed to undergo both creep and visco-plastic behaviour. As shown in Figures 3 and 4 the stress/strain relationship at any location along the adhesive layer was governed by the local adhesive strain rate (ie. the higher the local adhesive strain rate, the larger will be the apparent yield stress of the adhesive).

To determine how the rate-dependent adhesive properties affect the overall conclusion presented by Hart-Smith [4], the energy density at the worst point in the adhesive layer was also calculated. The results are shown in Table 3. The first observation, apparent from this Table, is that the energy density at the worst point is slightly higher when the ($L/2t$ ratio) is 7.5. Hence one would expect the joint with a lower ($L/2t$) ratio to have a slightly lower load carrying capacity. This has been shown in the experimental studies conducted by Wang and Kelly [10]. More importantly we find that, whilst the local stress/strain behaviour of the adhesive are largely dependent on the loading rate, the energy density at the worst point of the adhesive is relatively independent of the loading rate. There is only approximately 8% variation (refer to Table 3) in the energy density from the slowest to the fastest loading rate. Thus the formulae presented by the Hart-Smith [4] for estimating the load carrying capacity of a double lap joint appears to be valid when the joint is loaded in a truly monotonic fashion and when failure occurs in the adhesive.

A separate set of analyses were performed using similar joint configurations (ie. $L/2t=7.5$ and $L/2t=15$) under a more complex two stage loading process. In the first analysis, the initial load up from 0 - 350 MPa was undertaken in 1 sec (phase 1) and the final load up from 350 MPa to 422 MPa was attained in 100 sec (phase 2). In the second analysis, the initial load up from 0 - 50 MPa was undertaken in 100 sec (phase 1) and the load up from 350 MPa to 422 MPa took 1 sec (phase 2). The stress/strain behaviour at the worst point in the adhesive layer are shown in Figures 5 and 7. For comparison purposes the stress/strain curves for the cases when the load was increased from 0 - 422 MPa in both 1 and 100 sec are also included. As expected, the stress/strain behaviour of the adhesive is dependent on the loading history. Figure 5 also shows that during phase 1 of the loading, the stress/strain curve of the adhesive is similar to that when the joint was loaded from 0 - 422 MPa in 1 second. When the specimen undergoes the second phase of loading (350 - 422 MPa), the stress/strain behaviour of the adhesive tends towards the stress/strain curve when the joint was loaded from 0 - 422 MPa in 100 sec. It should also be noted that the final strain level attained by the adhesive is also slightly larger than when it was loaded monotonically from 0 - 422 MPa in 100 sec. The energy density at the worst point in the adhesive was also calculated and, for the first load case, the results are shown in Figure 6. For comparison the energy density curves for monotonic loading from 0 - 422 MPa in both 1 and 100 sec are also included in Figure 6. In this case the energy density calculated when the joint was loaded in this complex loading procedure is approximately 16 % higher than that calculated when the joint was monotonically loaded.

Table 3: Effect of loading rate on energy density both $L/2t=7.5$ and 15 at room temp.

Energy Density (MPa)	L/2t	Loading Time (sec)	0.1	1	10	100	% Diff
.	7.5	Adhesive layer	42.6	44.4	46.1	47.1	9.5
	15	Adhesive layer	41.6	43.7	44.9	45.1	7.8

Figure 2: A quarter of a symmetric double lap joint

Figure 3: Adhesive shear stress-strain curves at a critical point in the joint, $L/2t=15$.

Figure 4: Adhesive shear stress-strain curves at a critical point in the joint, $L/2t=7.5$.

Figure 5: Adhesive shear stress-strain curves at the critical point, $L/2t=15$, complex loading

Figure 7 shows the stress/strain behaviour of the adhesive at the worst point in the joint when it was loaded initially from 0 to 350 MPa in 100 sec (phase 1) and subsequently loaded from 350 MPa to 422 MPa in 1 sec (phase 2). The typical stress/strain behaviours at the same point when the joint is loaded from 0 to 422 MPa in 1 sec and 100 sec are included for comparison. As expected, the initial portion of the stress/strain curves under the first phase of the complex loading was similar to that when the joint was loaded monotonically from 0 - 422 MPa in 100 sec. However, when the loading rate was increased (ie. from 350 - 422 MPa in 1 sec), the stress/strain behaviour changes accordingly, and the local apparent yield stress of the adhesive was observed to have increased. Here the stress/strain curve of the adhesive during the second phase of the loading approaches its stress/strain curve when the joint was loaded monotonically from 0 - 422 MPa in 1 second.

The energy density curve calculated at the worst point of the adhesive is shown in Figure 8. Here the energy density curves for the cases when the joint was loaded from 0 - 422 MPa in 1 and in 100 sec are also included. It can be seen that the energy density of adhesive in the joint subjected to the complex load history is approximately 9 % less than that calculated when the joint was loaded up monotonically from 0 - 422 MPa in 100 seconds.

These analyses show that, at room temperature, when the loading history is simply monotonic the rate dependent properties of the adhesive in the double lap joint have limited effects on the load carrying capacity of the adhesive bond. However, when the joint is subjected to a complex monotonic loading history the time dependent properties of the adhesive should not be ignored.

Figure 6: Strain energy density at a critical point in the adhesive, $L/2t=15$, complex loading

Figure 7: Adhesive shear stress-strain at critical point, complex loading

Figure 8: Strain energy density at a critical point in the adhesive, $L/2t=15$, complex loading

CONCLUSION

This paper has revealed that the stress/strain behaviour of the adhesive in a double lap joint can be dependent on both the loading rate and the load history. At room temperature when the load is monotonic and has a constant loading rate the energy density at the worst point in the joint is almost time independent. When the joint is still loaded monotonically but in a complex manner then the load history dependent properties of the adhesive can become significant. This effect has implications for the fatigue assessment of bonded joints. It thus appears that, when performing a certification assessment which requires statements of the integrity and durability of adhesively bonded joints subjected to complex load spectra, it may be necessary to consider an analysis which accounts for both time and load history effects.

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REFERENCES

1. Hart-Smith, L.J. (1988), "Design and analysis of bonded repairs for metal aircraft structures", Chapter 3, *Bonded Repair of Aircraft Structures*, Edited by Baker, A.A. and R. Jones, Martinus Nijhoff, The Netherlands.
2. Jones R., Molent L., Paul J. J. , Saunders T., Chiu W. K, "Development of a composite repair and the associated inspection intervals for the F111C stiffener runout region", In *NASA Conference Publication 3274*, pp.339-350, 1994.
3. W. K. Chiu, P. D. Chalkley and R. Jones, "Effects of Temperature on the Shear Stress-Strain behaviour of Structural Adhesives (FM73) ", *Computers and Structures*, 53, 3, pp 483-489, 1994.
4. Stouffer, D.C. and Dame L. T., "Inelastic deformation of metals", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1996.
5. Ramaswamy, V.G. (1986), "A constitutive model for the inelastic multiaxial cyclic response of a nickel base superalloy Rene 80", *NASA*, CR-3998, 36.
6. Stouffer, D.C. and S.R. Bodner (1982), "A relationship between theory and experiment for a state variable constitutive equation", *Mechanical Testing for Deformation Model Development*, (Edited by R.W. Rhode and J.C. Swearingen), *ASTM STP 765*, 239-250.
7. Kuruppu, M.D., J.F. Williams, N. Bridgford, R. Jones, and D.C. Stouffer (1992), "Constitutive modelling of the elastic-plastic behaviour of 7050-T7451 aluminium alloy", *Journal of Strain Analysis*, 27, pp.85-92.
8. Jones, R., B. Trippit, W.K. Chiu, and J. Tomas (1995), "Lap joint theory revisited", *Polymers and Polymer Composites*, 3, pp.11-19.
9. Trippit, B. and R. Jones (1995), "Recent Australian developments in the engineering applications of constitutive modelling", *Numerical Implementation and Application of Constitutive Models in the Finite Element Method*, *ASME*, AMD-Vol. 213/MD-Vol.63, pp.15-20.
10. Wang, J. & D. Kelly (1996), "Experimental investigation on time-dependent behaviour of adhesively bonded joints", *Proceedings of the 2nd International Symposium on Aeronautical Science and Technology*, Indonesia, pp.630-645.